

VOLUME 32, ISSUE 3, JULY - SEPTEMBER, 2025

ISSN 0972-5563

Journal of Peace Studies

A QUARTERLY PEER - REVIEWED JOURNAL

A PEER- REVIEWED JOURNAL BY INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR PEACE STUDIES

ISSN 0972-5563

Journal of Peace Studies

VOLUME 32, ISSUE 3, JULY - SEPTEMBER, 2025

Journal of Peace Studies

C	O	N	T	E	N	T	S
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

From the Editors' Desk		1
ARTICLES		
Türkiye-Pakistan Strategic Partnership: Between Geopolitical Convergence and Identity Politics	<i>Md.Muddassir Quamar</i>	3
Resistance in Myanmar: Shaping New Political Realities in the Post Coup Era	<i>Munmun Majumdar</i>	31
Indian Diaspora's Role in Promoting Cultural Diplomacy in Central Asia	<i>Madhusmita Rout</i>	47
Regional Trade Agreements: Redefining Global Trade Networks in a Stagnant WTO Era	<i>Ajay Kumar Mishra & Shraddha Rishi</i>	60
Jammu and Kashmir's Changed Militancy Landscape: The Rise of Hybrid Militancy	<i>Toseef Ahmad Bhat</i>	82
STRATEGIC ESSAY		
Revisiting the Gurdaspur Award: Myths, Misconceptions and the Question of Kashmir's Accession	<i>Amit Krishankant Paul</i>	95
OPINION		
Bangladesh's Garment Industry: Between Empowerment and Exploitation	<i>Faiza Rizwan</i>	107
Bangladesh's Unfinished Revolution: Broken Promises, Rising Instability and Strained Ties with New Delhi	<i>Imran Khurshid</i>	114
BOOK REVIEW		
Middle of Diamond India: National Renaissance through Participation and Enerprise by Shashank Mani	<i>Harsh Pandey</i>	124

Journal of Peace Studies

FOUNDING EDITOR
LATE PROF. RIYAZ PUNJABI

ADVISORY BOARD
T. K. OOMMEN
RENÉ WADLOW
G BALACHANDRAN

EDITORIAL BOARD

NOOR A. BABA
AJAY DARSHAN BEHERA
UTTAM SINHA
SANJAY GUPTA

EDITOR (HONY)
ASHOK BEHURIA

CONSULTING EDITOR (HONY)
SMRUTI S. PATTANAİK

ASSOCIATE EDITOR
MOHMAD WASEEM MALLA

ASSISTANT EDITOR
PRATEEK JOSHI

DESIGN
BRINDA DATTA

PRINTED & PUBLISHED BY
SHEIKH KHALID JEHANGIR

International Centre for Peace Studies

Printed at:
A.M. Offsetters
Kotla Mubarakpur, New Delhi
PIN- 110 003, TEL: 2463 2395

Office Address:
157/9, Block 4, Second Floor,
Kishangarh, Vasant Kunj, New Delhi-
1110070

Regd. Address:
C-11 Jangpura Extension
New Delhi – 110 014
Tel: (91-11) 49989230, +91-9810317972
<http://www.icpsnet.org>
Emails: cpsndjps@gmail.com;
jps@icpsnet.org

SUBSCRIPTION

In India

This Copy	Rs. 350.00
Annual (Individual)	Rs. 1400.00
(Institutional)	Rs. 2000.00

Overseas (Air Mail)

This Copy:	US\$ 15.00 UK£ 9.00
Annual:	US\$ 60.00

Türkiye-Pakistan Strategic Partnership: Between Geopolitical Convergence and Identity Politics

Md. Muddassir Quamar*

Abstract

Historically anchored in Cold War political alignments and religious affinity, Türkiye-Pakistan relations have strengthened in the 21st century through expanding economic cooperation, mutual support in cross-border conflicts and growing security and defence ties. Given the longevity and magnitude of the ties, it can be defined as an enduring strategic partnership. From the perspective of International Relations scholarship, although this relationship is not bound by a formal pact which face periodic political and geopolitical challenges, it exemplifies alliance persistence, sustained by four interrelated factors of geopolitical alignment, geo-economic convergence, geostrategic collaboration and a shared commitment to identity politics. Beyond contributing to the literature on Türkiye-Pakistan relations, this article reinforces the constructivist view on alliance formation and persistence, particularly emphasising the role of shared identity.

Keywords: *Türkiye; Pakistan; identity; constructivism; alliance*

Introduction

Türkiye and Pakistan maintain robust political, economic, and security relations, underpinned by regular high-level diplomatic, political, and military engagements aimed at advancing shared

geopolitical, geo-economic, and geostrategic interests. Historically, the foundations of this partnership lay in a common geopolitical alignment with the West during the Cold War, primarily to counter Soviet expansionism, and in a shared sense of identity grounded in Islamic solidarity.¹ While the strategic

**Dr. Md. Muddassir Quamar is an Associate Professor at Centre for West Asian Studies, School of International Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India.*

imperative of balancing against the Soviet Union has long receded, the shared Islamic identity continues to shape bilateral interactions. In the post-Cold War era, this identity-based affinity has been complemented by a gradual deepening of security and defence cooperation alongside strengthened political and economic ties. These developments have reinforced what is often described as a strategic partnership that has endured since establishing diplomatic relations shortly after Pakistan's independence in 1947.² Although the relationship experienced some strains during the 1990s, as both states adjusted to shifting regional and international dynamics,³ it regained momentum in the early 2000s. Since then, Türkiye-Pakistan relations have weathered domestic,⁴ regional, and global challenges,⁵ emerging more resilient and multifaceted. In recent years, Türkiye has been seen as one of the closest friends of Pakistan, along with China.

From the perspective of International Relations literature, the Türkiye-Pakistan partnership may not qualify as an archetypal case of alliance, given the absence of a formal mutual defence pact or binding treaty. Yet, over decades, the continuity and depth of

engagements suggest an enduring strategic alignment rooted in more than transactional interests. This durability aligns with the concept of alliance persistence, which explains how partnerships can outlast their original strategic rationale through the interplay of multiple reinforcing factors. Examining this relationship through this alliance persistence lens offers a richer understanding of its longevity and adaptability across different historical and geopolitical contexts. It highlights how shared identity can serve as a stabilising force, complementing material interests and strategic calculations.⁶

An enduring strategic partnership

Türkiye and Pakistan enjoy longstanding bilateral relations rooted in historical ties, religious and cultural affinity, political understanding, strong trade and commercial linkages, and extensive defence and security cooperation.⁷ These relations gained strategic depth during the Cold War, as both Ankara and Islamabad gravitated towards Washington to counter the perceived threat from Moscow. Türkiye formally joined the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) in 1952, while Pakistan became a close ally of the United States (US) in South Asia, thereby

forging a close geopolitical bond between them.⁸ In 1955, the two, along with Iran, Iraq and the United Kingdom (UK), established the Middle East Treaty Organization (METO), also known as the Baghdad Pact, to strengthen regional security. The United States joined the alliance in 1959, but Iraq withdrew the same year following a coup that replaced the Hashemite monarchy with a Ba'athist regime. The pact was subsequently renamed the Central Treaty Organization (CENTO), in which Türkiye and Pakistan remained important members until its dissolution in 1979.

Besides geopolitics, geo-economics played a role in deepening their ties. Hence, in the 1960s, Türkiye, Iran and Pakistan formed the Regional Cooperation for Development (RCD) to harness the geo-economic opportunities in the Central Asia region, and foster trade, transport and infrastructure links. Although the RCD became defunct in 1979, it was replaced by the Economic Cooperation Organization (ECO) in 1985, which expanded in 1992 to include Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan after the Soviet Union's disintegration. ECO became a significant platform for advancing regional economic cooperation.⁹

The geopolitical and geo-economic alignment of the Cold War era, however, did not translate seamlessly into the post-Cold War order. The collapse of the Soviet Union altered regional dynamics, and Ankara and Islamabad faced the task of recalibrating their foreign policies. During the 1990s, bilateral relations experienced a relative stagnation, with divergences emerging on key issues, notably the Afghan conflict, where the two countries supported rival factions.¹⁰ Nevertheless, cordiality was maintained. A turning point came with General Pervez Musharraf's assumption of power in Pakistan in 1999. Having spent part of his childhood in Türkiye, Musharraf admired its socio-political transformation under Mustafa Kemal Atatürk and sought revitalising relations.¹¹ Within weeks of taking office, he visited Ankara to discuss Pakistan's political transformation.¹² This was followed by Turkish President Ahmet Necdet Sezer's visit to Islamabad in October 2001, focused on enhancing political and commercial ties.

The pace of engagement accelerated after *Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi* (Justice and Development Party, AKP) assumed power in Türkiye in November 2002. Under the AKP, Ankara recalibrated

its foreign policy to strengthen relations with neighbouring states and expand engagement with Asia and Africa, while pursuing European Union membership and maintaining strong ties with Washington. There was a palpable desire to reach out to Muslim countries to develop bilateral relations, and as such, the historically cordial ties created fertile ground for Ankara to develop an all-encompassing, stronger relationship with Islamabad.¹³ In May 2003, Turkish Foreign Minister Abdullah Gül visited Islamabad to explore avenues for deepening cooperation, paving the way for Prime Minister Recep Tayyip Erdoğan's visit in June 2003, just three months after taking office. Erdoğan was accompanied by a delegation of over 100 business leaders, underscoring the focus on trade and investment.¹⁴ Musharraf returned the visit in January 2004, becoming the first Pakistani leader to address the Turkish parliament. This visit proved crucial in strengthening security ties, leading to the signing of an MoU on "combating international terrorism" and agreements on intelligence sharing and expert exchanges.¹⁵

Between 2003 and 2025, as many as 28 high-level bilateral visits were exchanged between Ankara and Islamabad,¹⁶ besides hundreds of notable diplomatic, military and

business exchanges, not to mention the close people-to-people ties. These regular exchanges and contacts strengthened the bilateral relations. However, it is not only the regular diplomatic and political engagements that make the relations strategic. Four major factors contributed to the relations: political convergence and geopolitical alignment, economic cooperation and geo-economic confluence, defence and security collaborations, and a shared commitment to identity politics.

Without a formal alliance or strategic partnership agreement, these four factors helped deepen the strategic partnership. Literature on Türkiye-Pakistan relations underlines the significance of the strategic ties between the two without necessarily defining them as an alliance or partnership.¹⁷ A majority of the literature underlines the importance of deepening economic, political and security relations,¹⁸ while others locate the significance of the partnership in the context of the changing global and regional geopolitics.¹⁹ Yet others have noted the role of identity and Islamic solidarity in propelling the bilateral ties. There was a growing bonhomie between between Erdoğan and Imran Khan during the later's tenure as prime minister of Pakistan before

his government was removed in 2022 in a military influenced parliamentary no-confidence motion.²⁰ However, relatively few analyses explicitly conceptualise the relationship as a persistent strategic partnership, and even fewer systematically explore the role of shared identity as a sustaining factor.

Political convergence and geopolitical alignment

At the turn of the 21st century, Türkiye and Pakistan reinvigorated their bilateral ties, with regular high-level political visits serving as a critical mechanism for overcoming differences and creating platforms to address divergences. Sustained political and diplomatic engagement helped cultivate mutual understanding on a range of domestic, regional, and international issues. The cordiality of the relations was reflected in the aftermath of the devastating earthquake that hit Pakistan-occupied Kashmir (PoK) in October 2005. Only days after the disaster, Prime Minister Recep Tayyip Erdogan travelled to Islamabad to express solidarity, announcing a package worth US\$150 million, including US\$100 million in financial assistance and US\$50 million in relief goods. This

humanitarian gesture set the tone for a deeper phase of political contact.²¹

A key area of cooperation in the early 2000s was stabilising Afghanistan after the U.S.-led invasion in response to the 11 September 2001 (9/11) attacks. With the Taliban removed and a new US-backed government under Hamid Karzai installed in Kabul, Islamabad was compelled to adjust to the changed realities. Ankara actively facilitated Afghanistan-Pakistan reconciliation process,²² hosting a trilateral summit in 2007 where President Sezer hosted President Karzai and President Musharraf for a comprehensive dialogue concerning peace and security in Afghanistan. The meeting resulted in the Ankara Declaration, which emphasised “strengthening bilateral relations, territorial integrity, and non-interference in one another’s domestic affairs.”²³

Moreover, institutionalised cooperation frameworks emerged alongside these political gestures. The High-Level Military Dialogue Group (HLMDG) was formed in 2003, followed by an agreement on counterterrorism cooperation in 2004.²⁴ In 2009, the High-Level Cooperation Council (HLCC) was launched to explore the avenues for

expanding economic cooperation, meeting regularly thereafter.²⁵ Thus, in addition to stability in Afghanistan, institutionalised cooperation emerged as the key area for advancing political engagement. While political stability in Türkiye facilitated these mechanisms, Pakistan's domestic upheavals did not diminish its resolve, either in Islamabad or Rawalpindi, to maintain close ties with Ankara.

Political convergence between Türkiye and Pakistan has also been shaped by their respective responses to shifting regional and global developments. As Pakistan grappled with internal instability, its leadership sought external support for political and economic resilience, strengthening ties not only with the US and the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) but also with China and Türkiye.²⁶ Concurrently, the Justice and Development Party (AKP) under Erdogan sought to expand Ankara's influence in the Middle East, South Asia, and beyond, while balancing relations with the West. Nevertheless, their responses to the Arab Spring underlined a wide difference in approach, but one that complemented their foreign policy outlooks. While Ankara sought to capitalise on the uprisings to expand its influence in the Islamic world and emerge as a major Sunni-Muslim

power, Pakistan sought to remain neutral in regional rivalries, seeking a balanced approach towards three regional giants—Saudi Arabia, Iran and Türkiye. The divergence was most visible in 2015 when Pakistan declined to join the Saudi-led military intervention in Yemen, straining its ties with Riyadh and bringing it politically closer to Ankara.²⁷

A crucial moment in the Türkiye-Pakistan relations came in 2016 during the failed coup in Türkiye when Prime Minister Nawaz Sharif promptly called President Erdogan to express solidarity and condemn the coup attempt.²⁸ Soon after, Nawaz Sharif's brother, Shahbaz Sharif, then Chief Minister of Punjab province, visited Ankara to personally commend Erdogan for defeating anti-democratic forces. Reaching out to Erdoğan and expressing diplomatic and political solidarity helped strengthen the bonds further. In November 2016, Erdogan, accompanied by a large business delegation, undertook a two-day visit to Pakistan to thank the Pakistani leadership for supporting democracy in Türkiye. On the occasion, Erdogan was accorded the honour of addressing a joint session of Pakistan's parliament a third time.²⁹

Political convergence deepened further with the election of Imran

Khan in 2018. Soon after assuming premiership in August 2018, Khan announced his intention to enhance ties with the “brotherly” Türkiye and, within six months, in January 2019, visited Ankara amidst much fanfare.³⁰ Khan was accompanied by a delegation and held talks on bilateral issues, including enhancing economic and commercial relations and strengthening security and defence cooperation.³¹ Following the Erdogan-Khan meeting, the joint statement noted Turkish support for Pakistan’s Nuclear Suppliers Group (NSG) membership.³² Khan also thanked Türkiye for opposing Pakistan’s “grey-listing” by the Financial Action Task Force (FATF) in its plenary meeting in February 2018.³³ Erdogan paid a return visit in February 2020, focusing on furthering the political, economic and security cooperation.³⁴ Notably, a proposal for signing an agreement for granting dual citizenship to Pakistani immigrants in Türkiye was discussed.³⁵ Erdoan participated in the sixth Pakistan-Türkiye High Level Strategic Cooperation Council (HLSCC) meeting and addressed the Pakistani parliament for a record fourth time.³⁶ Moreover, Türkiye and Pakistan cooperated in combating COVID-19 and exchanged medical aid and expertise to deal with the global pandemic.

A key issue that animated Erdogan and Khan was Islamic solidarity, which became a tool for Türkiye to claim the leadership of the Sunni-Islamic world, directly challenging Saudi Arabia. The rhetoric leading up to the announcement of a parallel Islamic Summit in Malaysia in December 2019 underlined the growing political and geopolitical convergence of the two sides. However, at the same time, the Pakistani decision to abstain from the meeting at the last minute underlined the limits of the Ankara-Islamabad partnership.³⁷ Nonetheless, this did not disrupt the bilateral relations, neither did the change of government in Pakistan in 2022, as Shahbaz Sharif made two visits to Ankara in quick successions in June and November 2022 to seek continued political, economic and security cooperation and also invited Türkiye to participate in the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) to capitalise on the Chinese economic investments in Pakistan.³⁸

The political convergence goes beyond bilateral ties with a degree of geopolitical alignment and identity politics. As noted earlier, Ankara’s Islamic solidarity and leadership ambitions have played a role. Simultaneously, the two sides have developed a common

understanding of important regional issues by supporting each other's actions in the respective neighbourhoods. For instance, Islamabad has been supportive of Türkiye's actions in Syria and Iraq as well as the South Caucasus and Eastern Mediterranean.³⁹ In October 2019, when Ankara launched a military operation in northern Syria to neutralise the security threat emerging from the Kurdish People's Protection Unit (YPG),⁴⁰ Islamabad was among a few countries that extended support to the Turkish government.⁴¹ It also supports Türkiye in the fight against the Kurdish insurgency within and the targeting of the Kurdistan Workers' Party (PKK)⁴² safe havens in Iraq and Syria. Islamabad supports Ankara's actions in Northern Cyprus. Pakistani support for the Turkish military intervention in Libya and the military assistance to Azerbaijan during the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict in 2020 underlined the extent of geopolitical alignment. On the other hand, Ankara has extended support to Pakistan on its dispute with India over Kashmir, including over the withdrawal of Article 370 and in the wake of the Balakot air strikes in February 2019 and Operation Sindoor in May 2025. The two sought to develop cooperation in Afghanistan after the chaotic US withdrawal in August 2021.⁴³

The geopolitical alignment has expanded to include Azerbaijan, Afghanistan and Turkic-speaking countries in Central Asia. In the wake of the withdrawal of US and NATO forces and the dramatic rise of the Taliban on 15 August 2021, the Taliban took control of Kabul, and Ankara sought to develop a Türkiye-Pakistan-Taliban partnership to expand Turkish influence in South Asia. However, given the complexities involved, this has proven to be an extremely difficult task.⁴⁴ Besides, the Türkiye-Pakistan-Azerbaijan trilateral has made strategic inroads in the South Caucasus, as was noticed during the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict in 2020 and 2023. In the second Türkiye-Pakistan-Azerbaijan trilateral dialogue held in Islamabad in January 2021, the foreign ministers of the three countries "agreed to strengthen cooperation in diverse fields and people-to-people ties, as well as continue to support each other on all issues involving the three countries' national interests."⁴⁵

Türkiye's unwavering support for Pakistan on Kashmir stands out as both a geopolitical and identity-driven alignment, particularly following India's 2019 Article 370 abrogation to change of status of Jammu and Kashmir (J&K) when Pakistan's several other traditional

supporters, including the GCC countries, remained muted. Ankara's support for Islamabad over the Kashmir issue continued in the following years, including in the wake of the Pahalgam terror attack on 22 April 2025 and Operation Sindoor by the Indian armed forces to destroy terror bases in Pakistan.⁴⁶ This commitment has endured despite occasional tactical pragmatism, such as Prime Minister Bülent Ecevit's 2001 call for a bilateral resolution during his visit to India.⁴⁷ Under AKP leadership, however, Turkish backing has been explicit and unconditional. In fact, besides China, Türkiye and Malaysia were the only countries that extended support to Pakistan on Kashmir after New Delhi decided to end the special status of J&K.⁴⁸

President Erdogan has repeatedly raised the Kashmir issue at bilateral meetings and multilateral platforms, including several addresses to the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) since 2019.⁴⁹ This activism has strained Türkiye-India relations, prompting New Delhi to take exception to such overtures. For example, in October 2019, after Erdoan's speech in UNGA, the spokesperson of India's Ministry of External Affairs (MEA), during a weekly media briefing, stated: "We

call upon the Türkiye government to get a proper understanding of the situation on the ground before they make any further statements on this issue. It is a matter which is completely internal to India."⁵⁰ However, this did not deter Türkiye, and an almost similar situation arose during the UNGA Summit in September 2020 when Erdoan raised the Kashmir issue during his speech, which India termed "completely unacceptable."⁵¹ Again in February 2020, during his visit to Pakistan, Erdogan publicly raised the Kashmir conflict, including in the joint statement issued after the visit, which India firmly rejected. The MEA noted that "India rejects all references to Jammu and Kashmir," underlining that Kashmir "is an integral and inalienable part of India."⁵²

New Delhi has, on its part, taken steps to strengthen relations with Ankara's Eastern Mediterranean rivals – Greece and Cyprus – and enhance diplomatic engagement with Armenia. Moreover, India, in a first diplomatic offensive, issued a pointed criticism of Turkish military interventions in Syria and Libya.⁵³ Although a brief moderation in Erdoan's rhetoric was observed in 2021 and 2022 as part of a broader foreign policy recalibration, Türkiye returned to a more assertive stance during the Indo-Pakistani

Table 1:
Türkiye-Pakistan Bilateral Trade, 2000-2021 (US\$ million)

	Turkish Exports to Pakistan	Turkish Imports from Pakistan	Total Trade
2000	52.11	82.08	134.19
2001	31.19	101.28	132.47
2002	57.34	116.42	173.76
2003	70.35	192.03	262.38
2004	86.4	240.72	327.12
2005	187.55	315.46	503.01
2006	129.6	379.64	509.24
2007	157.04	531.62	688.66
2008	155.07	586.24	741.31
2009	162.51	619.22	781.73
2010	248.15	749.93	998.08
2011	213.67	873.13	1,086.8
2012	276.13	555.01	831.14
2013	285.9	436.65	722.55
2014	259.32	435.55	694.87
2015	289.15	310.54	599.69
2016	346.90	263.35	610.25
2017	352.17	323.12	675.29
2018	462.20	330.70	792.9
2019	550.16	306.26	856.42
2020	620.16	268.76	888.92
2021	773.08	314.81	1,087.89
2022	818.77	432.35	1,251.12
2023	550.46	455.50	905.96
2024	918.04	440.13	1,358.17

Source: Adapted from World Integrated Trade Solution (WITS), <https://wits.worldbank.org/CountryProfile/en/TUR>; and Turkish Statistical Institute, <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Foreign-Trade-Statistics-December-2020-37412&dil=2> (accessed 17 June December 2025).

military confrontation following the April 2025 Pahalgam terror attack. Ankara not only condemned Indian strikes under Operation Sindoor but reiterated its call for a resolution of the Kashmir dispute in line with Pakistan's position.

Economic and geo-economic cooperation

The second important component of the strategic partnership has been the economic and commercial relations that have witnessed significant progress in the past few years. Bilateral trade increased from US\$134.19 million in 2000 to US\$1.35 billion in 2024 (**Table 1**). Despite the global business slump due to Covid-19, Türkiye-Pakistan trade witnessed a notable growth between 2020 and 2022, and although it dipped somewhat in 2023, it picked up again in 2024, mainly on account of the robust Turkish exports, which increased from US\$289.15 million in 2015 to US\$918.04 million in 2024 (**Table 1**). Among the most important goods Turkish exports to Pakistan are defence equipment, machinery and electrical products, textiles and clothing, metals, chemicals, plastic and rubber, besides consumer goods, food products and other items. On the other hand, Turkish imports from Pakistan comprise textile and clothing,

consumer goods, plastic and rubber, food products, vegetables, chemicals and other items.⁵⁴

More than bilateral trade, it is the growing momentum in two-way investments, tourism and regional connectivity that is notable. Pakistan's economic woes have been exacerbated, resulting in serious financial challenges with rising external debts and a slump in growth. The financial situation has become graver because of the problems with GCC countries, especially Saudi Arabia and the UAE, which had traditionally supported the Pakistani economy by offering generous loans, grants, aid and trade, business and work opportunities for Pakistani citizens, generating massive remittances. The Pakistani economy has, therefore, become increasingly dependent on Chinese investments in the CPEC.⁵⁵ Besides China, Türkiye has been offering financial support to Pakistan by investing in the economy. Economic cooperation has been a constant area of discussion in bilateral talks. In February 2017, for example, Prime Minister Nawaz Sharif visited Ankara accompanied by a large business delegation. The focus of the visit was on promoting bilateral trade and commerce, and during his meeting with Erdogan, Sharif exchanged views on important

bilateral, regional and international issues.⁵⁶

As of 2024, over a hundred Turkish companies are doing business in Pakistan, and the cumulative Turkish foreign direct investment (FDI) in Pakistan has increased by nearly US\$1 billion, according to Pakistani sources. This is even though the Turkish economy has been struggling with serious financial challenges since 2016. Pakistan has invited Türkiye to invest in projects related to the CPEC and special economic zones (SEZs) across the country.⁵⁷ Notably, Türkiye and Pakistan intend to sign a free trade agreement (FTA), but it has not been realised due to concerns among Pakistani businesses regarding unfavourable terms. Meanwhile, the two have agreed to work under a Strategic Economic Framework (SEF) to boost bilateral trade and economic cooperation.⁵⁸

It is not only the bilateral economic cooperation that has strengthened the commercial ties. There is geo-economic convergence between Ankara and Islamabad in the Caspian and Central Asia region, wherein they wish to capitalise on China's economic investments through the Belt and Road (BRI) network and cooperation with countries like Russia and Iran. As

part of this, Türkiye and Pakistan have tried to revive the 10-member ECO. In early 2017, Erdogan visited Islamabad to attend the 13th summit of the ECO, wherein all ten heads of member states were present. A joint statement issued after the summit called for strengthening economic cooperation among the members and announced the adoption of the ECO Vision 2025.⁵⁹

Further, there are plans to boost regional connectivity and trade through multilateral cooperation with Iran, Central Asian republics, and even Afghanistan. For example, "in April 2019, Türkiye, Iran and Pakistan signed the International Road Transport agreement" to "open a direct Istanbul-Tehran-Islamabad trade corridor with smooth customs control, linking Türkiye, Central Asia and Europe."⁶⁰ A cargo train service from Islamabad to Ankara via Tehran became functional in December 2020.⁶¹ Besides, there are plans for Turkish involvement in the proposed Trans-Afghan railway and Central Asia-South Asia power projects (CASA-1000). Moreover, Türkiye and Pakistan are working together to enhance economic cooperation among countries in Central Asia and the South Caucasus, including Turkmenistan and Azerbaijan and have responded enthusiastically to China's BRI and the China-Central

Asia-West Asia Economic Corridor (CCAWEAC).⁶²

Security and defence collaborations

The third, and arguably most important, component of the Türkiye–Pakistan strategic partnership is security and defence cooperation. It spans defence manufacturing, arms trade, personnel training and joint exercises and shared threat perceptions in maritime security and counterterrorism areas. Over the past two decades, Türkiye has emerged as one of Pakistan’s principal arms suppliers. The Turkish defence industry has expanded rapidly in recent decades, with defence exports rising by 86 per cent between 2010 and 2019.⁶³ During this period, Pakistan ranked as the third largest recipient of Turkish arms and military equipment, accounting for nearly 11 per cent of Turkish total defence exports.⁶⁴ Between 2015 and 2019, Türkiye became the fifth-largest arms supplier to Pakistan, after China, Russia, Italy, and the United States. Some estimates suggest that in 2019–20, Türkiye was Pakistan’s second-largest arms exporter, trailing only China.⁶⁵

A series of high-profile defence deals illustrate the depth of this cooperation. Between 2011 and 2013,

Türkiye supplied 60 Panter 155mm towed guns to Pakistan under a 2009 agreement that included a production licence for domestic manufacture.⁶⁶ In 2015, Türkiye transferred 34 T-37B trainer aircraft to Pakistan. Between 2017 and 2018, Pakistan acquired 24 ASELPOD electro-optical targeting systems, valued at US\$50 million, for use on its JF-17 fighter aircraft.⁶⁷ Maritime cooperation has been equally significant. In 2018, the Pakistan Navy launched the replenishment tanker “PNS Moawin”, built at Karachi Shipyard and Engineering Works (KSEW) under a joint production agreement with Turkish defence firm STM.⁶⁸ The US\$80 million contract, signed in 2013, marked a milestone in bilateral naval collaboration. Again, in 2018, the two countries signed an agreement for four MILGEM-class frigates, to be delivered by 2023–25. Under the arrangement, two frigates are being built in Istanbul and two at KSEW. The first of the four frigates, PNS Babur, a 99-metre, 2,000-ton warship, was launched in Istanbul in August 2021 and is scheduled for induction into the Pakistan Navy in 2023.⁶⁹

In July 2018, Türkiye and Pakistan concluded a US\$1.5 billion agreement for 30 T-129 ‘Atak’ helicopters.⁷⁰ However, the deal stalled due to the US sanctions on few Turkish entities over the Ankara’s

procurement of the Russian S-400 missile defence system. The Pentagon's refusal to grant export licenses for US-made engines and components delayed delivery, prompting Türkiye to seek an extension.⁷¹ Defence manufacturer Turkish Aerospace Industries (TAI) has been involved in upgrading and maintaining Pakistan Air Force's (PAF) F-16s under a 2008 contract worth US\$64.5 million for 41 aircraft, renewed in 2016 to cover 74 aircraft.⁷² Reports also indicate Turkish assistance in upgrading three Pakistan Navy submarines.⁷³

Defence collaboration is not one-way. In 2016, Pakistan Aeronautical Complex (PAC) signed an agreement to supply 52 MFI-395 Super Mushshak trainer aircraft to the Turkish Air Force, with the first batch delivered in 2020.⁷⁴ In recent years, discussions have reportedly included joint production of fighter jets, ballistic missiles,⁷⁵ and drone components,⁷⁶ as well as the sale of Turkish unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to Pakistan.⁷⁷ At the same time, speculative reports have raised concerns about possible Pakistani assistance in enhancing Türkiye's nuclear capabilities, fuelling debates on proliferation risks.⁷⁸

Beyond procurement and manufacturing, the militaries of both

countries maintain extensive operational cooperation through regular joint exercises to build interoperability and share tactical expertise. In February 2021, Turkish and Pakistani Special Forces held ATATURK-XI – a three-week joint military exercise – in Pakistan's Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province.⁷⁹ In June 2021, PAF units participated in the International Anatolian Eagle-2021 exercise at Türkiye's 3rd Main Jet Base in Konya.⁸⁰ Such engagements have become a regular fixture of their bilateral defence relations.

Military training forms another vital component. According to some reports, since 2001, nearly 1,500 Pakistani military personnel have received training in Turkish institutions.⁸¹ Furthermore, naval cooperation is equally robust, symbolised by Turkish Navy's regular participation in AMAN multinational maritime exercise of Pakistan Navy since 2007.⁸² Both countries share a broadly similar threat perception regarding transnational terrorism, particularly the so-called Islamic State (ISIS). However, these convergences have not prevented either from being accused of providing, at times, covert or overt support to armed groups in theatres such as Syria, Afghanistan, and India.

Institutionalised frameworks anchor this cooperation as the Turkish and Pakistani military leadership regularly exchange views and have established strong relationships over the years besides engaging through bilateral military exercises, research, and training. The High-Level Military Dialogue Group (HLMDG), which convenes annually in alternating capitals, provides a platform for senior defence officials to coordinate policy. In December 2020, the HLMDG met in Ankara to discuss enhanced military cooperation and regional security challenges.⁸³ The 16th HLMDG meeting, held in Rawalpindi in January 2022, reaffirmed the commitment to sustained bilateral military-to-military engagements.⁸⁴ Security and defence cooperation are also discussed in other institutionalised mechanisms, such as High-Level Strategic Cooperation Council (HLSCC), which regularly meets at the summit level.⁸⁵

Strategically, the two militaries have cultivated a shared understanding of regional security threats and overlapping ambitions in South Asia, West Asia, and Central Asia. Türkiye's geopolitical and geo-economic interests in Central Asia align with Pakistan's longstanding influence in Afghanistan,⁸⁶ particularly during the Taliban's rule from 1996 to 2001 and again after their

return in 2021. For Ankara, expanding its footprint in Southwest Asia has meant becoming increasingly active in regional affairs, while Islamabad sees Türkiye as a valuable partner in projecting influence beyond South Asia.⁸⁷

Afghanistan, Central Asia, and the South Caucasus have traditionally been focal points of security cooperation. In the early 2000s, Türkiye played a mediating role between Afghanistan's new leadership and Pakistan following the US-led invasion of Afghanistan in 2001.⁸⁸ In the post-2021 environment, with the Taliban back in power and the US military withdrawn, the dynamic has shifted with Ankara now looking to Islamabad for support in maintaining a role in Afghanistan's political and security landscape even as Pakistan-Afghanistan relations remain comparatively strained. On 12 August 2021, just days before the Taliban's takeover of Kabul, Turkish Defence Minister Hulusi Akar visited Islamabad to discuss the evolving situation.⁸⁹ Then Pakistani Prime Minister Imran Khan urged Türkiye to take a direct role in preventing Afghanistan's descent into civil war. However, the optimism of 2021 has since moderated. A year into Taliban rule, Turkish enthusiasm for a deeper political or military role in Afghanistan has waned,

constrained by both the Taliban's insular policies and regional security complexities. Nevertheless, shared concerns, ranging from instability in Afghanistan to broader threats of terrorism and maritime insecurity, continue to underpin Ankara-Islamabad defence cooperation.

Commitment to Identity Politics

The fourth and final component of the enduring strategic partnership is a shared commitment to identity politics. Cultural, religious and civilisational connections are often cited as the basis of the bilateral ties between the two countries. However, more than the civilisational connection, it is the common feeling of being Sunni-Muslim republics with an Islamist-nationalist identity that has been instrumental in bringing them closer. Scholars have underlined the remarkable role of identity in Turkish domestic politics and foreign policy.⁹⁰ Nationalism and Islamism have been the most important components of politics and foreign policy in Türkiye since the AKP came to power. In the Pakistani case, the question of identity is more complex. It has often led to internal fissures in society and politics that have provided the opportunity for the Pakistani military to meddle in politics and control it.⁹¹ Islamic

identity has played a significant role in determining Pakistani foreign policy.⁹²

In both cases, the juxtaposition of identity with Islamic solidarity has played an important role in determining their national identities, as in foreign policy. The Islamic solidarity in foreign policy was overtly visible in the episode in December 2019 wherein the two, along with Malaysia, Qatar and Iran, tried to challenge Saudi Arabia's leadership of the OIC by organising a parallel Islamic summit in Kuala Lumpur in the wake of the extreme unease in Islamabad over the GCC countries' muted response to the Indian abrogation of Article 370. The idea to develop, or at least project, an alternative global Muslim leadership reflected the Islamist bonhomie between Erdogan and Khan. The two, along with Mahathir Mohammed of Malaysia, started discussing the need for fresh leadership for the Muslim world to address the conflicts and disputes. At the core of the issue was the perceived dissatisfaction in the larger Islamic world with the Saudi response, by way of its leadership in the OIC and the League of Arab States, to "burning" conflicts in Palestine and Kashmir.⁹³

The parallel summit created a serious churn in the relationship

between Riyadh and Islamabad, with Saudi Arabia making it clear that the summit would be seen as challenging the kingdom's leadership of the Islamic world. Khan backed out of attending the meeting at the last minute, making the event a damp squib and underlining the limitations of the Türkiye-Pakistan strategic partnership. At the same time, the incident did not significantly harm the bilateral ties between the two countries, underlying its inherent endurance. Islamabad continued to court Erdoan, particularly because of the Pakistani frustration over the Arab countries adopting a neutral position on J&K, seen in Islamabad as an affront.⁹⁴ Contradictorily, Ankara remained steadfast in its support of Pakistan over the Kashmir issue, given the "brotherly" ties implying Islamic solidarity. The shared commitment to identity politics is also visible in the regular people-to-people contacts and cultural affinity with notable consumption of Pakistani and Turkish TV series and films by the population of both countries.

Conclusion

Türkiye and Pakistan have, in recent decades, significantly improved their bilateral relations. Under the AKP government in Ankara since 2002, bilateral relations

have expanded in multiple areas to attain the status of a strategic partnership. In a way, this is a continuation of the partnership between the two that was visible during the Cold War due to their alignment with the West. Hence, with an interruption in the 1990s, the Türkiye-Pakistan strategic partnership has witnessed continuity, making them a case of an enduring partnership. Typically, from the point of view of International Relations literature, this may not be considered a case of alliance persistence. However, a certain case for an enduring strategic partnership can be made. Through a systematic discussion, this article underlines the significance of four factors, namely geopolitical alignment, geo-economic convergence, geostrategic collaboration and a shared commitment to identity politics, which have contributed to the persistence of the Türkiye-Pakistan strategic partnership. Besides underlining the significance of the combination of these factors in the sustenance of the partnership, this article also confirms what is already known and discussed in constructivist debates on the significance of the identity factor in alliance formation and persistence. Hence, identity is not only an important factor in sustaining the

strategic partnership between Türkiye and Pakistan, but from the point of view of International Relations literature, this reinforces the significance of identity in alliance formation and persistence.

References

1. Naved Ahmad, 'Pakistan-Turkey Relations', *Pakistan Horizon*, 34(1), (1981), pp.105–128; Nadia Mushtaq, 'Pak-Turkey Relations: Towards a Cooperative Future', *Strategic Studies*, 24(2), (2004), pp.89–116.
2. Selçuk Çolakolu and Emre Tunç Sokaolu, 'Turkey-Pakistan Relations: Towards Multidimensional Regional Integration', *Muslims Perspectives*, 1(2), (2016), pp.1–40; Sheharyar Khan, 'Dynamics of Pakistan-Turkey Relations', *Pakistan Review of Social Sciences*, 1(2), (2020), pp.14–24.
3. Ishtiaq Ahmed, 'Turkey and Pakistan: Bridging the Growing Divergence', *Perceptions: Journal of International Affairs*, 5(3), (2000), pp.1–9.
4. Since November 2002, Türkiye has elected an Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi (Justice and Development Party; AKP)-led government headed first briefly by Abdullah Gül as prime minister (November 2002-March 2003), and since March 2003 led by Recep Tayyip Erdoğan, first as prime minister (2003-2014) and later as president (2014 onwards). During August 2014 and July 2018, Erdoğan was not the formal head of the government but controlled it as the most important figure of the AKP and since May 2017 as Leader of the AKP. Pakistan, on the other hand, has had several governments, initially under General Pervez Musharraf's military rule (1999-2008) and subsequently elected governments led by Prime Ministers Nawaz Sharif (2013-2017), Imran Khan (2018-2022) and Shahbaz Sharif (2022-).
5. Mushtaq, 'Pak-Turkey Relations', pp.89–110; Çolakolu & Sakaolu, 'Turkey-Pakistan Relations', pp.1–37.
6. Alexander Wendt, 'Collective Identity Formation and the International State', *The American Political Science Review*, 88(2), (1994), pp.384–96.
7. Çolakolu & Sakaolu, 'Turkey-Pakistan Relations', pp.1–37; Khan, 'Dynamics of Pakistan-Turkey', pp. 14–24; Maria Hassan, *Türkiye-Pakistan Relations in the Context of Changing International System: Regional and*

- Global Implications, Master Thesis, Bursa Uludag University, Turkey, 2022, pp. 14–20; Agha Hussain, 'Turkey's Relations with Pakistan: Friends, But not Allies,' King Faisal Center for Research and Islamic Studies, Riyadh, (2022), pp.1–8, <https://kfcris.com/pdf/fc636965a37bee99b11d6cc00035004f6327254b9ac24.pdf> (accessed 5 November 2023).
8. Ahmad, 'Pakistan-Turkey Relations', pp.109–10; Çolakolu & Sakaolu, 'Turkey-Pakistan Relations', pp.2–4.
 9. Anas Haroon and Yunus Özcan, 'Economic Relationship between Turkey and Pakistan', *0_letme*, 2(2), (2021), pp.1–13.
 10. Ahmed, 'Turkey and Pakistan'; Hussain, 'Turkey's Relations with Pakistan'.
 11. Ilene R. Prusher, 'A Turkish Path for Pakistan?', *The Christian Science Monitor*, (24 January 2002), <https://www.csmonitor.com/2002/0124/p01s04-wosc.html> (accessed 5 November 2023).
 12. Mushtaq, 'Pak-Turkey Relations', p.94.
 13. Emre Hatipoglu and Glenn Palmer, 'Contextualizing Change in Turkish Foreign Policy', *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, 29(1), (2016), pp.231–250; Alexander Murinson, 'Strategic Depth Doctrine of Turkish Foreign Policy', *Middle Eastern Studies*, 42(6), (2006), pp.945–964.
 14. Al Jazeera, 'Turkish PM praises Pakistan 'Reforms'', (16 June 2003), <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2003/6/16/turkish-pm-praises-pakistan-reforms> (accessed 5 November 2023).
 15. Mushtaq, 'Pak-Turkey Relations', pp.95–96; Dawn, 'Cooperation with Turkey', (19 June 2003), <https://www.dawn.com/news/1064680> (accessed 5 November 2023).
 16. Erdoan has visited Pakistan as many as 11 times between 2003 and 2022—seven times as prime minister, including in June 2003, October 2005, October 2009, October 2010, May 2012, November 2012 and December 2013, and four times as president, including in August 2015, November 2016, February 2017, February 2020 and February 2025. Meanwhile, five presidential and seven prime ministerial visits have occurred from Pakistan to Türkiye. Musharraf visited Ankara twice as president in 2004 and 2007 and President Mamnoon Hussain visited Ankara in July 2018 to attend the

swearing-in ceremony of Erdoğan. In October 2018, President Arif Alvi travelled to Istanbul to attend the inauguration of the new international airport and reception for the 95th Republic Day of Türkiye. President Alvi again visited Ankara in August 2021 to attend the launch of “the first of the four MILGEM-class corvette ships built by Türkiye for Pakistan”, as noted by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Republic of Türkiye. Nawaz Sharif visited Türkiye four times as prime minister, while Imran Khan’s maiden visit to Ankara was in January 2019. Shahbaz Sharif, who succeeded Khan in April 2022, has since undertaken six visits to Türkiye in June and November 2022, in February and May 2023 and again in April and May 2025.

17. Çolakolu & Sakaolu, ‘Turkey-Pakistan Relations’; Khan, ‘Dynamics of Pakistan-Turkey’; Hassan, Türkiye-Pakistan Relations; Hussain, ‘Turkey’s Relations with Pakistan’.
18. Ishrat Afshan Abbasi, Mukesh Kumar Khatwani and Muhammad Ramzan Kolachi, ‘Pakistan-Turkey Relations: Political and Economic Dimensions,’ *Grassroots*, 54(1), (2020), pp.69–80; Haroon & Özcan, ‘Economic Relationship between Turkey’, pp.1–13.
19. Vinay Kaura, ‘The Erdogan Effect: Turkey’s Relations with Pakistan and India’, ISAS Working Paper No. 36, (16 October 2020), pp.1–10, <https://www.isas.nus.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/336.pdf> (accessed 5 November 2023); Hassan, Türkiye-Pakistan Relations, pp.14–20; Hussain, ‘Turkey’s Relations with Pakistan’, pp.1–6.
20. Rahat Shah, ‘Explaining Pakistan-Turkish Relations: Islamism and Naya Pakistan’, *Asian Journal of Middle Eastern and Islamic Studies*, 16(1), (2022), pp.113–125.
21. Dawn, ‘Turkey Offers \$150m Relief’, (21 October 2005), <https://www.dawn.com/news/162218/turkey-offers-150m-relief> (accessed 5 November 2023).
22. Çolakolu & Sakaolu, ‘Turkey-Pakistan Relations’.
23. Selçuk Çolakolu, ‘Turkey-Pakistan Security Relations since the 1950s’, Middle East Institute, Washington, D.C., (25 November 2013), <https://www.mei.edu/publications/turkey-pakistan-security-relations-1950s> (accessed 5 November 2023).

24. Ibid.
25. Abbasi, Khatwani & Kolachi, 'Pakistan-Turkey Relations', 73–4.
26. Syed Mohammad Ali, 'The U.S.-China Strategic Rivalry and its Implications for Pakistan', Stimson Center, Washington, D.C., (1 December 2020), <https://www.stimson.org/2020/the-u-s-china-strategic-rivalry-and-its-implications-for-pakistan/> (accessed 5 November 2023); Haroon & Özcan, "Economic Relationship between Turkey," 1–13.
27. Khalid Iqbal, 'Yemen Crisis and Pakistan: A Holistic Overview', *Policy Perspectives*, 12(2), (2015), pp.61–80; Mahjoob Zweiri and Thomas Bonnie James, 'Saudi-Pakistan Relations: An Age of Uncertainty or Decline?', *Contemporary Review of the Middle East*, 8(4), (2021), pp. 496–511.
28. TRT World, 'How the world reacted to the 2016 coup attempt in Turkey', (12 July 2017), <https://www.trtworld.com/turkey/how-the-world-reacted-to-the-july-15-coup-attempt-in-turkey-398998> (accessed 5 November 2023).
29. Abrar Saeed, 'Erdogan first head of state to address joint session thrice', *The Nation*, (14 November 2016), <https://nation.com.pk/14-Nov-2016/erdogan-first-head-of-state-to-address-joint-session-thrice> (accessed 5 November 2023).
30. Abbas Shabbir, 'PM Khan Arrives in Turkey for Two-Day Visit', *Samaa*, (3 January 2019), <https://www.samaaenglish.tv/news/1644727/pm-imran-khan-and-president-erdogan-to-have-one-on-one-meeting-during-his-visit-to-turkey> (accessed 5 November 2023).
31. Dawn, 'PM Khan Reaches Turkey on two-day visit, pays homage to Maulana Rumi', (3 January 2019), <https://www.dawn.com/news/1455232> (accessed 5 November 2023).
32. The News International, 'Pakistan-Turkey joint statement on PM Imran Khan's visit to Turkey', (4 January 2019), <https://www.thenews.com.pk/latest/414711-pakistan-turkey-joint-statement-on-pm-imran-khans-visit-to-turkey> (accessed 5 November 2023).
33. Dawn, 'PM Khan Reaches Turkey'.
34. Sabena Siddiqui, 'Erdogan to discuss trade, military plans in Pakistan', *Al-Monitor*, (11 February 2020), <https://www.al-monitor.com/pulse/>

- originals/2020/02/erdogan-turkey-discuss-trade-military-pakistan-china.html (accessed 5 November 2023).
35. Saima Shabbir, 'Officials confirm agreement with Turkey on dual nationality under consideration', Arab News, (1 February 2020), <https://www.arabnews.pk/node/1621411/pakistan> (accessed 5 November 2023).
36. Aamir Latif, 'Erdogan to address Pakistan's parliament on 16 February', Anadolu Agency, (6 February 2020), <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/asia-pacific/erdogan-to-address-pakistans-parliament-on-feb-14/1726687> (accessed 5 November 2023).
37. Hussain, "Turkey's Relations with Pakistan," pp. 1-6.
38. Dawn, 'PM Shehbaz invites Turkiye to join CPEC', (25 November 2022), <https://www.dawn.com/news/1722996> (accessed 5 November 2023).
39. Sanaullah Khan, 'PM Imran Assures Erdogan of Pakistan's Support, Solidarity over Turkey's Syria Operation', Dawn, (11 October 2019), <https://www.dawn.com/news/1510278> (accessed 5 November 2023); Aamir Latif, 'Pakistan Backs Turkey's Anti-Terror Fight in Syria', Anadolu Agency, (14 February 2020), <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/asia-pacific/pakistan-backs-turkeys-anti-terror-fight-in-syria-/1734417#> (accessed 5 November 2023).
40. Ankara views the YPG as a front for the Democratic Union Party (PYD), the Syrian branch of the Kurdistan Workers' Party (PKK), which is outlawed in Turkey and is regarded as a terrorist organization by the US, UK, Canada, Japan, Australia and EU.
41. The News International, 'PM Imran telephones Erdogan, assures full support to Turkey', (11 October 2019), <https://www.thenews.com.pk/amp/539756-pm-imran-telephones-erdogan-assures-full-support-to-turkey> (accessed 5 November 2023).
42. The PKK announced its disbandment on 12 May 2025.
43. Md. Muddassir Quamar, 'Turkish and Iranian Response to Upheaval in Afghanistan', Manohar Parrikar Institute for Defence Studies and Analysis, New Delhi, (3 September 2021), <https://idsa.in/idsacomments/turkish-and-iranian-response-afghanistan-mmquamar> (accessed 5 November 2023). Metin Gurcan, 'Ankara Mulls Ambitious but Risky Engagement with Taliban', *Al-Monitor*, (18 August 2021), <https://www.al-monitor.com/>

originals/2021/08/ankara-mulls-ambitious-risky-engagement-taliban
(accessed 5 November 2023).

44. Galip Dalay, 'Will Turkey's Afghanistan ambitions backfire?', Chatham House, London, (6 October 2021), <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2021/10/will-turkeys-afghanistan-ambitions-backfire> (accessed 5 November 2023).
45. Naveed Siddiqui, 'Pakistan, Turkey, Azerbaijan resolve to enhance cooperation, continue mutual support on national issues', Dawn, (13 January 2021), <https://www.dawn.com/news/1601304/pakistan-turkey-azerbaijan-resolve-to-enhance-cooperation-continue-mutual-support-on-national-issues> (accessed 5 November 2023).
46. Rahul Roy-Chaudhury, 'India-Pakistan drone and missile conflict: differing and disputed narratives', The International Institute for Strategic Studies, London, (15 May 2025), <https://www.iiss.org/online-analysis/online-analysis/2025/05/indiapakistan-drone-and-missile-conflict-differing-and-disputed-narratives/> (accessed 17 June 2025).
47. Kaura, 'The Erdogan Effect', p.1.
48. Nur Bü_rä Bilgiç and Gözde Bayar, 'Turkish, Pakistani leaders discuss India's Kashmir move', Anadolu Agency, (6 August 2019), <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/asia-pacific/turkish-pakistani-leaders-discuss-india-s-kashmir-move/1550414> (accessed 5 November 2023).
49. United Nations, 'Turkey - President Addresses General Debate, 74th Session', YouTube, (24 September 2019), <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Bve1yt0SEb4> (accessed 5 November 2023).
50. Geeta Mohan, 'Understand Kashmir situation before making further comments: MEA tells Turkey', India Today, (4 October 2019), <https://www.indiatoday.in/india/story/understand-kashmir-situation-before-further-comments-mea-tells-turkey-1606302-2019-10-04> (accessed 5 November 2023).
51. Business Standard, 'India slams Erdogan's Kashmir remarks at UNGA, call it 'gross interference'', (23 September 2020), https://www.business-standard.com/article/international/india-slams-erdogan-s-kashmir-remarks-at-unga-call-it-gross-interference-120092300127_1.html (accessed 5 November 2023).

52. Ministry of External Affairs, India [MEA, India], 'Official Spokesperson's response to queries on references to Jammu & Kashmir by the Turkish president and the Turkey-Pakistan joint declaration', (15 February 2020),
53. MEA, India, 'Unilateral Military Offensive by Turkey', (10 October 2019), <https://www.mea.gov.in/press-releases.htm?dtl/31926/unilateral+military+offensive+by+turkey> (accessed 5 November 2023); The Times of India, 'India Attacks Turkey for 'Disregarding' UN on Libya', (1 September 2022), <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/india-attacks-turkey-for-disregarding-un-on-libya/articleshow/93914896.cms> (accessed 5 November 2023).
54. World Bank. "World Integrated Trade Solution", <https://wits.worldbank.org/CountryProfile/en/TUR> (accessed 12 December 2022).
55. Nick Macfie, 'China's Li offers to help end Pakistan energy crisis', Reuters, (22 May 2013), <https://web.archive.org/web/20131230003027/http://www.reuters.com/article/2013/05/22/us-pakistan-china-idUSBRE94L06G20130522> (accessed 5 November 2023); Harsh V. Pant, 'Pakistan's Growing Reliance on China', Observer Research Foundation, New Delhi, (10 August 2018), <https://www.orfonline.org/research/pakistans-growing-reliance-on-china/> (accessed 5 November 2023).
56. Daily Sabah, 'Pakistani PM Visits Turkish parliament bombed on 15 July coup attempt', (23 February 2017), <https://www.dailysabah.com/diplomacy/2017/02/23/pakistani-pm-visits-turkish-parliament-bombed-on-july-15-coup-attempt> (accessed 12 December 2022).
57. Tuba Shahin, "Turkish President's Pakistan visit to enhance trade relations", Anadolu Agency, (13 February 2020), <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/economy/turkish-president-s-pakistan-visit-to-enhance-trade-relations/1732856> (accessed 12 December 2022).
58. Daily Sabah, 'Ankara, Islamabad eager to bolster already strong economic relations', (13 February 2020), <https://www.dailysabah.com/business/2020/02/13/ankara-islamabad-eager-to-bolster-already-strong-economic-relations> (accessed 12 December 2022).
59. Islamuddin Sajid and Aamir Latif, 'Erdogan arrives in Pakistan to attend economic summit', Anadolu Agency, (13 February 2020), <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/asia-pacific/erdogan-arrives-in-pakistan-on-2-day->

- official-visit/1733024# (accessed 12 December 2022).
60. TRT World, "Turkey and Pakistan agreement is a win-win for both nations", (14 February 2020), <https://www.trtworld.com/turkey/turkey-and-pakistan-agreement-is-a-win-win-for-both-nations-33798> (accessed 12 December 2022).
61. Sahar Khan, 'The untapped economic potential of the Pakistan-Turkey relationship', *South Asian Voices*, (20 April 2021), <https://southasianvoices.org/the-untapped-economic-potential-of-the-pakistan-turkey-relationship/> (accessed 12 December 2022).
62. Selçuk Çolakolu, *Turkey and China: Political, Economic, and Strategic Aspects of the Relationship* (Singapore: World Scientific, 2021), pp.105–25.
63. Lucie Béraud-Sudreau et al., 'Emerging Suppliers in the Global Arms Trade', *SIPRI Insights on Peace and Security*, No. 2020/13, (December 2020),
64. *Ibid.*, p.8.
65. Siddiqui, 'Erdogan to discuss trade'.
66. Stockholm International Peace Research Institute [SIPRI], 'Arms Transfer Database', <https://www.sipri.org/databases/armstransfers> (accessed 29 December 2022).
67. *Ibid.*
68. STM, 'Pakistan Navy Fleet Tanker Project: PNS Moawin', <https://www.stm.com.tr/en/our-solutions/naval-engineering/pakistan-navy-fleet-tanker-project> (accessed 29 December 2022).
69. Tim Fish, 'Pakistan, Turkey tighten ties with first corvette launch', *Breaking Defense*, (23 August 2021), <https://breakingdefense.com/2021/08/pakistan-turkey-tighten-ties-with-first-corvette-launch/> (accessed 29 December 2022).
70. Defence Turkey, 'Pakistan and Turkey sign a contract for the procurement of T129 'Atak' helicopters', (11-15 June 2018), <https://www.defenceturkey.com/en/content/pakistan-and-turkey-sign-a-contract-for-the-procurement-of-t129-atak-helicopters-3029> (accessed 29 December 2022).
71. Anwar Iqbal, 'Pakistan gives another extension to helicopter deal with Turkey', *Dawn*, (17 March 2021), <https://www.dawn.com/news/1612986>

(accessed 29 December 2022).

72. Burak Ege Bekdil, 'TAI talks to upgrade Pakistani F-16s', *Defense News*, (24 May 2016), <https://www.defensenews.com/air/2016/05/24/tai-in-talks-to-upgrade-pakistani-f-16s/> (accessed 29 December 2022).
73. Daily Sabah, 'Turkey, Pakistan relations peak with defence industry cooperation', (13 February 2020), <https://www.dailysabah.com/defense/2020/02/13/turkey-pakistan-relations-peak-with-defense-industry-cooperation> (accessed 5 November 2023).
74. Cem Akalin and Ibrahim Sunnetci, 'PAC to initiate the delivery of MFI-395 Super Mushshak to the Turkish Air Force in June 2020', *Defence Turkey*, 14(96), (2019), pp.30–31, <https://www.defenceturkey.com/files/issues/5e01cfb1ee025.pdf> (accessed 29 December 2022).
75. Selcan Hacaoglu, 'Turkey widens war tech hunt by tapping Pakistan's China ties', *Bloomberg*, (2 March 2021), <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2021-03-02/turkey-expands-war-tech-search-by-tapping-pakistan-s-china-ties> (accessed 29 December 2022).
76. Presidency of the Republic of Turkey, 'It is obligation for us to be strong in military, economic and diplomatic terms', (23 January 2021), <https://www.tccb.gov.tr/en/news/542/123664/-it-is-an-obligation-for-us-to-be-strong-in-military-economic-and-diplomatic-terms-> (accessed 29 December 2022).
77. Lennart Hofman, 'How Turkey became a drone power (and what that tells us about the future of warfare)', *The Correspondent*, Translated from the Dutch by Anne Hodgkinson, (10 December 2020), <https://thecorrespondent.com/832/how-turkey-became-a-drone-power-and-what-that-tells-us-about-the-future-of-warfare/110071049088-d67e839e> (accessed 29 December 2022); Daily Sabah, 'Turkish aerospace, Pakistani institution to jointly produce UAV parts', (22 August 2021), <https://www.dailysabah.com/business/defense/turkish-aerospace-pakistani-institution-to-jointly-produce-uav-parts> (accessed 29 December 2022).
78. S. D. Pradhan, 'Emerging Sino-Pak-North Korea-Turkey nexus for nuclear proliferation', *The Times of India*, (27 January 2021), <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/ChanakyaCode/emerging-sino-pak-north-korea-turkey-nexus-for-nuclear-proliferation/> (accessed 29 December 2022).

79. Aamir Latif, 'Turkey-Pakistan joint military exercise begins', Anadolu Agency, (9 February 2021), <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/asia-pacific/turkey-pakistan-joint-military-exercise-begins/2138335> (accessed 29 December 2022).
80. Defence Turkey, 'The International Anatolian Eagle-2021 exercise begins in June with the participation of allied countries', (18 June 2021), <https://www.defenceturkey.com/en/content/the-international-anatolian-eagle-2021-exercise-begins-in-june-with-the-participation-of-allied-countries-4608> (accessed 29 December 2022).
81. Siddiqui, "Erdogan to discuss trade."
82. 0brahim Sünnetçi, "'Together for Peace" AMAN-19 multinational naval exercise & Pakistan – Turkey defence cooperation', Defence Turkey, 13(91), (2019), pp.22–50, https://www.defenceturkey.com/files/issues/DT_91_web.pdf (accessed 12 December 2022).
83. The News International, 'Pak-Turkey military dialogue group's 15th meeting held in Ankara', (25 December 2020), <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/764011-pak-turkey-military-dialogue-group-s-15th-meeting-held-in-ankara> (accessed 12 December 2022).
84. The National Frontier, 'Pakistan, Turkey hold High Level Military Dialogue', (6 January 2022), <https://thenationalfrontier.com/2022/01/06/pakistan-turkey-hold-high-level-military-dialogue/> (accessed 12 December 2022).
85. Latif, 'Turkey-Pakistan joint military'.
86. Brent E. Sasley, 'Turkey in Central Asia: Turkish Identity as Enabler or Impediment', in Emilian Kavalski, ed., *The New Central Asia: The Regional Impact of International Actors* (Singapore: World Scientific, 2010), pp.191–214.
87. Çolakolu, 'Turkey-Pakistan security relations'.
88. Ibid.
89. Al-Monitor, 'Turkey's defense minister discusses Afghan security in visit to Pakistan', (12 August 2021), <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2021/08/turkeys-defense-minister-discusses-afghan-security-visit-pakistan#ixzz74iSDttVT> (accessed 5 November 2023).

90. Yücel Bozdaliolu, 'Modernity, Identity and Turkey's Foreign Policy', *Insight Turkey*, 10(1), (2008), pp.55–75; Martina Warning, and Tuncay Karda_, 'The Impact of Changing Islamic Identity in Turkey's New Foreign Policy', *Alternatives: Turkish Journal of International Relations*, 10(2-3), (2011), pp.123–40; Soner Cagaptay, *The New Sultan: Erdogan and the Crisis of Modern Turkey* (London: I. B. Tauris, 2017); Ceren Lord, *Religious Politics in Turkey: From Birth of the Republic to the AKP* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2018).
91. Mazhar Aziz, *Military Control in Pakistan: The Parallel State* (London: Routledge, 2007).
92. Sisir Gupta, 'Islam as a Factor in Pakistan's Foreign Policy', in Donald Eugene Smith, ed., *South Asian Politics and Religion* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1966), pp.428–50; S. Akbar Zaidi, 'South Asia? West Asia? Pakistan: Location, Identity', *Economic and Political Weekly*, 44(10), (2009), pp.7–13.
93. Umer Karim, 'Who can lead the Muslim world? The view from Islamabad', *LSE Blogs*, (13 February 2020), <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/mec/2020/02/13/who-can-lead-the-muslim-world-the-view-from-islamabad/> (accessed 12 December 2022).
94. Dipanjan Roy Chaudhury, 'In balancing act, Pakistan to host Recep Tayyip Erdogan in Feb', *The Economic Times*, (31 December 2019), <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/international/world-news/in-balancing-act-pakistan-to-host-recep-tayyip-erdogan-in-feb/articleshow/73039964.cms?from=mdr> (accessed 12 December 2022).

Note for readers and subscribers

We are happy to inform you that from January 2009 we have introduced the system of peer review of articles to ensure quality of publications and improve the scholarly value of our journal. We have a renowned group of scholars and academicians associated with our Centre and they are helping us in this process. We are grateful to them for their kind support and cooperation.

We would request our readers and subscribers to take note of these changes and we would, as ever, encourage them to send in research articles for publication to us. The manuscripts of research papers submitted for publication should be neatly typed in double space and the length of the papers should be ideally between 3,000-5000 words including the references. They should contain an abstract and a short introduction of the author. The authors should use Chicago Manual Style for their references. The articles can be sent to us in an electronic format, preferably Ms Word. For detailed guidelines they may send their queries to us in the following address.

Journal of Peace Studies Research Section

Emails: cpsndjps@gmail.com, jps@icpsnet.org

Registered with the Registrar of Newspapers
RNI No. 57199/93

INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR PEACE STUDIES

C-11, Jangpura Extension,
New Delhi – 110 014, INDIA

Tel: (91-11) 49989230, +91-9560126157, 9810317972

Websites: <http://www.icpsnet.org> (Main),
www.icpsorg.com (Kashmir chapter)

Emails: cpsndjps@gmail.com, jps@icpsnet.org